

Comparitive Study on Wireless and Wireline Services in Reliance Communications Ltd, Chennai, Tamilnadu

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Dr. S. Saravanan

Assistant Professor & Research Supervisor

PG & Research Department of Commerce, Dr.Ambedkar Government Arts College Vyasarpadi, Chennai

Dr. S. Velayutham

Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration,

Mohamed Sathak College of Arts and Science, Sholinganallur, Chennai

Abstract

Telecommunications is one of the sectors that encountered a boom after the early 90's. There has been lot of improvements in this sector in terms of the tariffs and the technology we are currently. But this sector has seen unprecedented rise in the number of players operating in the market, bringing in the best of tariffs, services and as well as bringing down the profits of the companies. My project aims to do a comparative study on the Wire line and wireless products in Reliance Communication, Chennai. This project is done with a sample size of around 50 companies from different profiles like infrastructure, financial services, banking, IT & ITES etc. A basic understanding of these companies are done by finding out details like number of branches they have in the city, the number of telecom services they use and the overall expenses they incur for these services in a year. The methodology included meeting the companies, conducting interviews with the personnel with the help of a structured questionnaire. Sample size is 50 and the sampling technique is judgement sampling. Inferences from the research said that Airtel was rated best among the specified competitors. Airtel USP was their customer service, Reliance's USP was pricing and technical support, TATA had its core competitiveness in pricing. Suggestions were to improve the roll out of network by Airtel and TATA to reduce network congestion and improve their network service. BSNL need to be more a customer oriented company. Reliance has to improve upon its quickness in solving a query with improve in customer care and Airtel has to reduce its pricing based on the consuming capabilities of the customer.

Keywords: Reliance Communication, Wireless and Wireline service.

Introduction

Indian telecommunication Industry is one of the fastest growing telecom markets in the world. From the status of state monopoly with very limited growth, it has grown in to the level of an industry. Telephone, whether fixed landline or mobile, is an essential necessity for the people of India. This changing phase was possible with the economic development that followed the process of structuring the

economy in the capitalistic pattern. Removal of restrictions on foreign capital investment and industrial de-licensing resulted in fast growth of this sector. Currently, India has the third largest (based on the total number of fixed/mobile subscriber lines) telecom network in the world and the second largest mobile network. The mobile sector has grown from around 10 million subscribers in 2002 to reach 375 million at the end of Feb 2011. The two major reasons that have fuelled this growth are low tariffs coupled with falling handset prices. The total number of telephone lines was over 413 m at the end of Feb 2011.

India has opted for the use of both the GSM (global system for mobile communications) and CDMA (code-division multiple access) technologies in the mobile sector. Fixed Line Telephony can be further categorized as fixed wire line telephony and fixed wireless telephony (known as WLL (F)). Fixed Line Telephony provides services such as local calls and long distance calls-national and international. The Government of India is now taking actions to convert all national long distance calls to local calls. In this regard, Public Players have already started their 1Rs. call service. In India at present, fixed line telephone numbers are of 8 digits, (initially 5 and 7 digits). The sector is in the process of converting all fixed line numbers to 10 digits. Recently there has been a move to convert all the mobile numbers to 11 digits. Both Public Players and Private Players are competing hard to capture more and more market share. MTNL and BSNL are the leading public sector players, whereas Reliance Communications, Tata Teleservices, Vodafone and Airtel are the leading private sector players.

Identified Problem

During the course of study the following problems were identified:

- Lack of awareness among users about the tariffs of competitors
- Lack of interest among users towards surveys
- Confusion among users regarding which service provider had better tariff plans
- Users were unable to map the quality of service of competing players

Need for Study

This study was needed for understanding the response pattern among consumers towards the services provided by various competing wire line companies in the city of Chennai. Through this one can have a clear understanding on the comparison between the competing brands, their pros and cons. The comparison would in turn help users and prospective users in having a clear choice when it comes to picking the service provider best suited to their needs.

Objectives

- To assess the awareness levels of users in Chennai on various wire line service providers
- To have a comparative study on the competing wire line service providers
- To seek an in-depth knowledge about the consumer attributes towards the services provided by major wire line brands
- To quantify, analyse & interpret the results so as to have a clear understanding of the pros and cons of each service provider

Methodology

Target respondents: Corporate and their branches which use wire line service from one of the service provider namely Reliance, Airtel, Tata or BSNL. The billing amount per month should be more than 5 lakhs to be included as a sample. The reason for considering the lower ceiling is that a sample should do substantial amount of business to understand the service and hence a proper response in the questionnaire.

Sampling Methods: The 50 samples taken for analysis is a representative of the entire Chennai region in terms of the quality of service provided by the wire line operators. The limit of 5 lakh is set so that sample considered has enough knowledge to comment about the service, and proper responses can be obtained.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The Questionnaire was given to around a sample size of 50, and the output from the questionnaire is represented in terms of a pie chart for proper understanding and inferences. The analysis is done by taking into account six variables, i.e.

- 1) Rating the service providers in terms of courteous response provided by the customer care
- 2) Which service is more quicker in resolving complaints
- 3) Which service provides the best coordination from the assurance managers
- 4) Which service has the best coordination in terms of technical assistance
- 5) Who gives the most competitive tariff
- 6) Who is the best service provider overall.

Diagrammatic Representations and Inferences

Table 1 Courteous Response of Customer Care

S.No	Subscriber	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Airtel	25	50
2	Reliance	15	30
3	TATA	7	14
4	BSNL	3	6

From the responses received, Airtel clearly has an upper hand over other competitors Reliance, TATA and BSNL. Almost 50% accepted that Airtel has a very good customer care service and a good after sale service. This response reinstates the fact that apart from the good products that Airtel gives it is backed up excellent customer care to stay on top of the Indian market. TATA Communications and BSNL hold a very low position with BSNL staying at the bottom. This specifies that the government held BSNL still stays a long way from the private players for eg Airtel or Reliance. It was astonishing that TATA Communications came last among the private players with a very low percentage compared to Airtel and Reliance.

Table 2 Quickness in Resolving Complaints

S.No.	Subscriber	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Airtel	20	40
2	Reliance	15	30
3	TATA	10	20
4	BSNL	5	10

As a continuation to the first factor, this second factor checks which company resolves complaints quicker. Airtel ranks first because due to their excellent customer care and process involved in closing of a query. Moreover the CRM processes used by Airtel are the best in the Industry. BSNL bags only 10% of the sample as a service which is quick in responding to complaints. Once again this can be attributed to the poor customer care mechanism that BSNL has. Reliance comes second

behind Airtel, although their processes are the best in the industry there is always a time lag in closure of a call, especially a complaint. TATA comes third and the last among private players. As mentioned earlier customer care is not their USP, therefore TATA comes third in resolving the quickness of a query.

Table 3 Best Coordination from Assurance Managers

S.No.	Subscriber	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Airtel	17	34
2	Reliance	17	34
3	TATA	13	26
4	BSNL	3	6

For all the key accounts an accounts manager is nominated so that he takes care of those accounts. Similarly, for service assurance in these clients an assurance manager is nominated. Whenever there is any issue regarding services, big clients hold their assurance managers responsible. In this criteria, Airtel and Reliance make sure that churn level is minimal or nil. Both score an equal 34% for the coordination given by the assurance manager in offering services or while resolving complaints. Once again BSNL scores the lowest in this and TATA comes third but very close to Airtel and Reliance. What can be understood is, all the three private players lay more emphasis on providing services by assurance managers so that the big clients don't leave them.

Table 4 Best Coordination in Terms of Technical Assistance

S.No.	Subscriber	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Airtel	15	30
2	Reliance	20	40
3	TATA	10	20
4	BSNL	5	10

This one of the USP of Reliance Communication, Reliance according to the requirements of the customer can technically design the products and make it suit customer needs. Airtel comes second in this regard. Although they are brilliant in providing technical assistance to the clients, to design products to suit the needs of customer is not their USP. BSNL comes last in the list with very less technical assistance in case of any service issues. TATA once gain ranks last in private players.

Table 5 Competitive Tariff

S.No.	Subscriber	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Airtel	8	16
2	Reliance	20	40
3	TATA	20	40
4	BSNL	2	4

Market leader Airtel comes last among the private players, and the companies that give a very competitive pricing to the clients are TATA and Reliance. The USP of TATA and Reliance that

can be seen from the above is its pricing. Airtel commands a premium pricing for the same services given by its competitors simply because of its excellent customer care services. In this department both TATA and Reliance come second and third respectively. BSNL scores last in this. They are out priced by their competitors in this factor also.

Table 6 Service Provider Rating

S.No.	Subscriber	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Airtel	20	40
2	Reliance	17	34
3	TATA	8	16
4	BSNL	5	10

When the companies are ranked in the overall, i.e. in all factors like service, products, pricing, technical support etc Airtel comes first closely followed Reliance. BSNL and TATA comes a disappointing last as they are not able to garner up any USP for themselves, although TATA has the pricing factor as their USP. Reliance comes a close second with pricing and technical assurance to the clients. The main thing that can be understood is, although Airtel comes last in pricing they are most preferred by customers due to their excellent after sales service.

Findings

1. BSNL is yet to evolve in any of the factors like product development, customer service, technical support, assurance etc
2. Reliance and TATA telecommunications’ main aim or objective was to induce more churn into Airtel’s customers by having a very low pricing.
3. Almost all the corporate liked Reliance for its ability to design any kind of products and solutions for the customers, but was worried with the after sale service support.
4. It was evident that reliance had to improve its customer care support
5. TATA communications was very strong in its Data side(Internet services)
6. BSNL was just an also ran in the most competitive sector in India.

Suggestions and Recommendations

1. The recommendation given for TATA was to implement or improve their network roll out so that they could improve on their voice aspects.
2. BSNL should be a more customer oriented company if they have to stay in this highly competitive market. The reason being that they score very less in all factors.

Conclusion

Numerous studies and trends show that wireless services are replacing wire line services. This paper offers statistically significant evidence that a change in wire line prices would produce a large Increase in wireless demand. That fact, supported by a host of studies from other sources, suggests that wireless services are replacing wire line services. In addition to wireless competition, broadband and VoIP competitors are beginning to provide traditional wire line services with stiff intermodal competition. If wire line providers are unable to raise prices without creating a significant decline in demand, as shown in this paper, then intermodal competition mitigates the presence of market power and, therefore, the need for government regulation of the telecommunications marketplace.

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